

Final Manuscript Version –

Ocean & Coastal Management, Ocean and Coastal Management 268 (2025) 107756
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2025.107756>

Assessing cumulative risks to coastal and marine habitats under management and climate change scenarios: The case of northern Portugal

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Graphical Abstract

Abstract

Managing the risks associated with human activities and uses in marine and coastal regions is crucial in a time of maritime activity expansion promoted by Blue Growth, especially with the increasing effects of climate change. Effective management of the cumulative risks is essential to safeguard ecosystems from potential further degradation, maintaining their resilience and ability to provide ecosystem services (ES) and societal goods and benefits (SGB). Here, we adopt a cumulative risk-based approach to assess risk to habitats and ecosystems, considering human activities and two climate-derived pressures for three management narratives, across three IPCC Shared Socioeconomic Pathways in the northern marine and coastal region of Portugal. Our findings highlight high ecosystem risk in some marine areas and coastal segments, particularly affecting beaches, aphotic soft and rock bottoms, and estuarine areas. Across the management and climate scenarios, the most important contributors to risk included rising sea surface temperatures, increased coastal exposure to relative sea-level rise (SLR) and storminess, fishing, tourism, artificial areas, and maritime transport. Overall spatial risk patterns varied more

with changes in management scenarios than between climate scenarios, with climate pressures having an additive effect on habitat and ecosystem risk. The inclusion of the climate-derived exogenous pressures (i.e. those whose causes emanate from outside the management system) altered the high-risk zone spatial patterns at the land-sea interface, while in marine areas, it increased the overall risk scores without changing the observed overall risk patterns. It is recommended that policymakers and managers should adopt a precautionary approach, using cumulative assessments integrated into decision-support systems and ecosystem-based management plans to anticipate and adapt to or mitigate future changes. Thereby, ensuring the maintenance of the ecosystem resilience to change, to avoid reaching tipping points that would disrupt the resource-provisioning capacity of these ecosystems and the provision of ES and SGB.

Keywords: maritime spatial planning, ecosystem-based management, ecosystem services, societal goods and benefits.

Introduction

Managing marine resources and the pressures of human activities on the ocean natural capital is a current global concern (Halpern et al., 2019; United Nations, 2021). In particular, spatially-explicit risk mapping of human activities that create pressures on ecosystems is essential for policymakers and managers to ensure and maintain sustainable use of resources, while sustaining human activities that support the livelihoods of coastal to global communities (Cormier et al., 2022; Elliott, 2023; Elliott and Kennish, 2024; Mangano et al., 2020). Hazards occur in coastal and marine areas either naturally or through human activities and these produce risks if they lead to adverse effects on human welfare (Cormier et al., 2013; Elliott et al., 2019; Elliott and Kennish, 2024). Understanding and quantifying those risks and then either adapting to them or mitigating their effects is key to marine and coastal management (Elliott and Kennish, 2024). Explicit knowledge of habitats and ecosystems and their biological infrastructure, and most importantly of the existing pressures to their conservation is essential for achieving the goals of European legislation (Berg et al., 2015; EU, 2008; Frazão Santos et al., 2018), such as, for example the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, EU, 2008), or the Biodiversity Strategy targets for

2030 (European Commission, 2021). This is also aligned with global initiatives such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, the Convention on Biological Diversity, or the Global Biodiversity Framework (Cormier and Elliott, 2017; Molony et al., 2022).

Maritime spatial planning (MSP) emerges as a valuable tool to manage marine uses and activities, that at nearshore areas, coupled with Integrated Coastal Management (ICM) and other coastal and land planning instruments can address conflicts between conservation and the overexploitation of marine and coastal resources, and achieve and maintain a Good Environmental Status (GES) promoted by the MSFD; in Europe, MSP is operationalised through the MSP Directive (EU, 2014). It plays a key role in regulating the spatial jurisdiction of maritime activities across various sectors, offering a strategic approach to balance the needs of both conservation and human use in marine environments. Spatially-explicit risk mapping from regional to local scales is essential to the implementation of these policies and contribute to the protection and maintenance of GES, ensuring ecosystem functioning and the sustainable capacity to provide valuable ecosystem services (ES) and societal goods and benefits (SGB) (Barbier, 2017; Elliott, 2023; Halpern et al., 2015).

With approximately one third of the global population living within 100 km of the coast, and with the numbers projected to rise (Small and Nicholls, 2003), there is an urgent need for policymakers, managers, and stakeholders to enhance their understanding of the management of these systems to ensure their resilience and ability to deliver ES and SGB (Barbier, 2017; Culhane et al., 2018; Galparsoro et al., 2021). Moreover, this is especially the case with the increasing pressures posed by climate change, such as rising sea temperatures and sea level, the emergence of anoxic zones, and increased extreme events (Koenigstein et al., 2016; Vargas et al., 2017; Vedor et al., 2021). These combined stressors can lead to synergistic, complex and non-linear impacts on coastal and marine ecosystems, compromising their resistance and resilience, in which resilience is define as the ability to recover from stressor effects, in contrast to the resistance to such effects (Elliott and Kennish, 2024; Gissi et al., 2021; Hewitt et al., 2016; IPCC, 2014). Additionally, these stressors may create further habitat loss, ecological damage, and unpredictable cascading effects within these ecosystems, which compromise the delivery of the ES and SGB upon which socio-economic systems and local communities depend (Elliott and O'Higgins, 2020; Gregr et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2025). Although of high current concern, the combined analysis of human pressures and effects

and climate change is still seldom performed (Borja et al., 2024; Gissi et al., 2021; Simeoni et al., 2023). In addition, while our understanding of the potential future consequences of stressors on ecosystems and species still remains poorly understood (Gissi et al., 2021; Hewitt et al., 2016), particularly the interactions and potential synergies between multiple stressors, as well as the responses from ecosystems, there is an increasing need to identify current high-risk areas for timely activity management (Vinebrooke et al., 2004; Jackson et al., 2021; Simmons et al., 2021; Vos et al., 2023). This could prove invaluable for managing in an integrated manner, providing the necessary tools and information for better future planning, and also for monitoring progress towards management objectives (Borja et al., 2024; Cormier and Elliott, 2017; Elliott et al., 2025).

In response to escalating human activities promoted by Blue Growth and the Blue Economy (European Commission, 2012) and the anticipated future impacts of climate change, this study aimed to conduct a regional-scale spatially-explicit risk assessment from current human activities, considering the future IPCC AR6 climatic scenarios in Portugal (IPCC, 2023; Voltaire et al., 2019), encompassing potential climate change-induced stressors, along several management narratives. This study has two primary objectives: i) to evaluate the primary areas of risk to ecosystems arising from current human activities across different management narratives, and ii) to analyse changes in the distribution of risk areas with the incorporation of climate-derived pressures. By evaluating both current and future risks to coastal and marine ecosystems, these spatially explicit risk assessments can empower managers to make informed decisions to promote sustainable activities practices and mitigation approaches that could enhance the adaptive capacity of coastal and marine systems to the increasing pressures posed by climate change and other anthropogenic pressures.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Methodological approach

To evaluate the cumulative effects of ongoing human activities and anticipated climate change impacts on coastal and marine habitats, we used a cumulative risk approach using the InVEST® Habitat Risk Assessment (HRA) model (version 3.14) (Arkema et al., 2014; Natural Capital Project, 2023). This is supported by well-established cumulative principles derived from risk

literature applied in ecological risk management (Arkema et al., 2014, 2015; Field et al., 2014; Samhoury and Levin, 2012). This model calculates the risk posed by each stressor to individual habitats, i.e. the probability that the specific stressor will reduce the quality of habitat, combining different criteria of exposure (the probability of an event happening) and consequences (the habitat-specific response to stressors). The final risk-computation integrates spatially explicit and non-spatial data, generating scores for each habitat-stressor pairing. This approach yields spatially explicit risk scores for the case study area, providing valuable insights to inform management (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Figure of the methodological approach used in this study.

2.2 Study area

The northern Portuguese marine and coastal region serves as the case study for assessing the potential threats posed by various activities and their pressures, including climate change (Figure 2). The region extends from the Minho estuary in the north, which borders Spain, to the coastal limits of Porto Metropolitan Area. This region stands as a prominent hub for industrial operations

and shipping, in particular housing the major commercial ports in Matosinhos and Viana do Castelo, as well as extensive urbanized areas. Additionally, several significant protected areas focus on safeguarding vital estuarine and coastal regions, including two marine protected areas (MPAs). One of these MPAs is the Parque Litoral Norte MPA (PNLN), encompassing 77 km² of marine area and 18 km of coastline. The other MPA, the Maceda/Praia da Vieira Site was designated by Portugal and the European Commission as a Site of Community Importance, emphasizing cetacean conservation (Figure 2). The case study area spans 5140 km², extending from the national territorial water limits (at 12 nautical miles from the coastal baseline) to a 500 m buffer zone around estuarine bodies and the coastline, delineating the areas covered by the current coastal and estuarine management plans.

Figure 2. Location of the study area in the northern coast of Portugal, with the location of the current protected areas and marine protected area boundaries indicated. PNLN – Parque Natural do Litoral Norte.

2.3 Data collection

2.3.1 Habitats

The case study area encompasses diverse habitats, including coastal and nearshore environments, offshore benthic areas, and pelagic zones, comprising a total of 12 primary habitat types: (1) saltmarshes, (2) coastal dunes, (3) beaches, (4) intertidal rocks, (5) intertidal sands, (6) estuarine bottoms, (7) photic soft bottoms, (8) photic rock bottoms, (9) aphotic soft bottoms, (10) aphotic rock bottoms, (11) the estuarine pelagic realm, and (12) the marine pelagic realm (Table S1, Figure S1). Data regarding marine bottom type were sourced from EUSeaMap (Vasquez et al., 2021) and simplified to hard and soft bottoms. They were further categorized into photic and aphotic zones, considering the 25 m water depth, approximately the known limit of photosynthetic light reaching the seabed in this region. The pelagic environment was subdivided into estuarine and marine pelagic water habitats. Coastal and nearshore habitats data were obtained either from the 2018 national land cover dataset (DGT <https://dgterritorio.gov.pt/dados-abertos>) or extracted from orthophotos of the study area coastline (Cunha et al., 2021).

2.3.2 Sources of pressure

The evaluation of cumulative risk to habitats in the study area was conducted using spatially explicit data (i.e. the extents or so-called footprints) of human activities and uses, compiled from multiple sources (Table 1, Figures S2 to S6). This analysis considered both the manageable human activities and uses (10 stressors) and the unmanageable or exogenic threats arising from climate change-derived pressures (2 stressors) (Elliott, 2011). The term exogenic is used for those pressures whose cause is outside the management area but whose consequences are within the area (Elliott and Kennish, 2024). The stressor spatial information was used as provided by the supplier, except in the cases where the stressor had spatially explicit information on the stressor intensity. In these cases, stressor intensity information was reclassified into 4 intensity bins (see Supplementary Material). It is of note that no spatial distribution on the intensity of local small-scale fishing was available for the study case area. It is acknowledged that the extents (footprints) of pressures and their effects will be greater than the activity footprints (Elliott et al., 2020), but unless indicated below, in the absence of more detailed information, the spatial and temporal extent of the activity is used as a proxy for those pressures and effects footprints.

Table 1. List of manageable and unmanageable stressors used in this study. The Buffer column indicates the buffer applied for the defined stressor area, in the cumulative risk calculation, when applicable. SEC – Spatially Explicit Criteria, indicates whether there are spatial variations in activity intensity across the stressor distribution. MSP – Maritime Spatial Planning.

Type	Name	Data source	Buffer (meters)	SEC
Manageable stressors	Aquaculture	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	500	No
	Material disposable areas	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	500	No
	Ports	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	1000	No
	Extraction of materials	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	500	No
	Surfing areas	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	0	No
	Recreation - beaches	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	250	No
	Discharge location points	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	1000	No
	Wind energy facilities	Portuguese MSP (https://psoem.pt)	500	No
	Agricultural areas	Portuguese land cover map	1000	No
	Urban or artificial areas	Portuguese land cover map	1000	No
	Maritime transport	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities	0	Yes
	Maritime transport - recreational	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities	0	Yes
	Maritime transport - other	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities	0	Yes
	Fishing - dredges	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes
	Fishing - drifting longlines	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes
	Fishing - purse seines	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes
	Fishing - gillnets	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes
	Fishing - longlines	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes
	Fishing - trawlers	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes
Fishing - unknown gear	https://globalfishingwatch.org/	0	Yes	
Unmanageable stressors	Coastal Vulnerability Index	Cunha et al., (2021)	0	Yes
	Sea Surface Temperature (SST) scenarios	Voltaire et al., (2019) (https://aims2.llnl.gov/search)	0	Yes

2.4 Risk assessment

The risk posed by the selected stressors to the habitats in the study area was assessed by calculating Exposure and Consequence criteria for each habitat-stressor combination using the InVEST HRA (Tables S2 and S3). Exposure criteria considered parameters related to habitat vulnerability, including spatial or temporal overlap, stressor intensity, and the effectiveness of existing management strategies. Consequence criteria considered the effects of stressors on habitats, encompassing potential changes in habitat area or structure, disturbance frequency, habitat recovery time, and connectivity (Natural Capital Project, 2023).

The risk assessment model followed a four-step process: (1) calculation of Exposure and Consequence scores for each habitat-stressor pair, (2) use of Exposure and Consequence scores for each habitat-stressor pair to calculate the risk score, (3) calculation of the cumulative risk score for each habitat at each grid location, and (4) calculation of an Integrative risk index – Ecosystem Risk, across all habitats in a grid cell. A qualitative scale ranging from 0 to 3 was employed to assess all Exposure and Consequence criteria for each habitat-stressor pair. This assessment was conducted using expert knowledge and peer-reviewed literature (when available), following the methodology outlined in Kappel et al., (2012).

Within each grid cell, if there is a spatial overlap between the stressor and the habitat, the overall weighted averages of the Exposure and Consequence were computed as follows (1):

$$E_{jkl} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{e_{ijkl}}{d_{ijkl} \cdot w_{ijkl}}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{d_{ijkl} \cdot w_{ijkl}}}, \text{ and } C_{jkl} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{c_{ijkl}}{d_{ijkl} \cdot w_{ijkl}}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{d_{ijkl} \cdot w_{ijkl}}}, \quad (1)$$

where, E_{jkl} and C_{jkl} represent the Exposure and Consequence scores, respectively, specific to habitat j from stressor k in location l ; e_{ijkl} and c_{ijkl} denote the specific ratings for exposure and consequence; d_{ijkl} represents the data quality rating, and w_{ijkl} is the importance weighting for the criterion (Natural Capital Project, 2023).

The risk of each stressor to each habitat was determined as a distance-weighted risk value at each grid cell. The Euclidean approach was employed, offering a more conservative, precautionary, and additive method for the cumulative risk calculation (Arkema et al., 2014; Halpern and Fujita, 2013;

Samhoury and Levin, 2012). The risk (R_{jkl}) for each habitat (j), from the stressor (k) at the grid cell (l) was calculated as follows (2):

$$R_{jkl} = \sqrt{(E_{jkl} - 1)^2 + (C_{jkl} - 1)^2} \cdot D_{jkl}, \quad (2)$$

where D_{jkl} , represents a decay function. In this study, the data sources were used as provided (Table 1), except in cases where the potential pressure of the activity could extend beyond its activity footprint (Elliott et al., 2020). For such instances, a distance buffer was incorporated, and a linear decay function was applied within the buffer, where the stressor effects diminish linearly with the distance to the stressor. The linear decay function was computed as (3):

$$D_{jkl} = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{\text{distance}_{jkl}}{\text{bufferdist}_k} & \text{if } \text{distance}_{jkl} > \text{bufferdist}_k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The cumulative risk to each habitat j from all stressors k at each grid cell l was then calculated as (4):

$$R_{jl} = \sum_{k=1}^K R_{jkl} \quad (4)$$

And the cumulative risk to the ecosystem from all stressors k to all habitats j at each grid cell l , is given by (5):

$$R_l = \sum_{j=1}^J R_{jl} \quad (5)$$

For comparison between different scenario narratives, the final cumulative risk to the ecosystem from each scenario was classified into three classes (low, medium, and high risk), based on the risk percentiles of the Current narrative risk scores. Specifically, the classification was as follows: low risk was assigned to grid cells corresponding to risk percentiles <25%, medium risk included values between $\geq 25\%$ and <75% of the risk percentiles, and high risk comprises values $\geq 75\%$ of risk percentile.

2.5 Management and climatic scenarios

To assist decision-makers and managers, we developed different management scenario narratives based on expert judgement of the area and potential future scenarios (Table 2, Figure S7). These

narratives represent different perspectives on regional management, ranging from changing the intensity of human activity to prioritizing the protection of the region natural capital and balancing of human activities. The scenarios encompass:

(1) the current situation (denoted as Current), with the existing human activities (Table 1) and current intensity (on a 0 to 3 scale);

(2) a business-as-usual scenario, (labelled BAU), where human activity footprints are maintained (Table 1) but intensity is increased by 1 point, assuming an increase of human activity and uses in the future;

(3) a semi-protection scenario (MPA1), where the PNLN MPA boundaries were expanded to include significant near-shore rock seabed formations along the coast up to the Minho estuary (Figure S7, centre), prohibiting only large-scale fishing within the MPA boundaries, while maintaining current activity levels otherwise;

(4) a protection scenario (MPA2), expanding the boundaries of the Maceda MPA to the limits of the Portuguese Territorial waters near the Minho estuary (Figure S7, right) and completely restricting fishing (no-take zone) within the extended MPA boundaries, and

(5) a variation of scenario (4), denoted as MPA2rf, with the extension of the Maceda MPA as in the scenario MPA2, but large-scale fishing inside was allowed at a low intensity of 1 (on a 0 to 3 scale).

For each management scenario narrative, we have also modelled the added climate-derived pressures of SST (sea-surface temperature) and Coastal Vulnerability to sea level rise (SLR) and extreme events, for three Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) AR6 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) outlined in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, namely the SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5 scenarios for the years 2050 and 2100 (IPCC, 2023). This meant that 7 potential climate scenarios were modelled for each one of the 5 management narratives, namely: 1) Present climatic conditions, 2) SSP1-2.6 2050, 3) SSP2-4.5 2050, 4) SSP5-8.5 2050, 5) SSP1-2.6 2100, 6) SSP2-4.5 2100, 7) SSP5-8.5 2100, for a total of 35 risk assessment scenarios.

Table 2. Description of the 5 management narratives used in this study and the acronyms used. Please note that for each one of these management narratives all the 6 AR6 SSP scenarios were also run, for a total of 35 risk assessment scenarios.

Acronym	Management Narrative scenarios	Description
Current	Current Management Scenario	- Current activity intensity
BAU	Business-as-usual Scenario	- Increase of all activity intensity (by 1, on a 0-3 scale)
MPA1	Present + Protection of important rock bottoms	- Maintenance of current activities intensity - Increasing PNLN boundaries to important near-shore rock seabed formations up to Minho estuary
MPA2	Present + Expansion of MPA - No large-scale Fishing	- Maintenance of current activities intensity - Increasing Maceda MPA boundaries up to Minho estuary
MPA2rf	Present + Expansion of MPA - Reduced large-scale Fishing	- Maintenance of current activities intensity - Increasing Maceda MPA boundaries up to Minho estuary - Reduction of fishing inside MPA (Intensity = 1)

3 Results

3.1 Management narratives ecosystem risk

The cumulative risk assessment showed different spatial patterns of risk across the study area and across the different management narratives considered. There were coastal and marine regions where the cumulative risk from the different pressures was low in the Current management narrative (Figure 3). This includes some of the nearshore marine regions and other offshore marine areas, where there was a low occurrence or lower intensity of human activities and uses. On the other hand, some marine regions were shown to be at higher cumulative risk, highlighting the value of cumulatively assessing multiple pressures. These “hotspots” of risk were particularly noticeable where multiple human activities and uses are cumulatively occurring. For example, in the southern marine region, the spatial overlap of multiple fishing gears was observed, with the

additional occurrence of marine activities and uses such as maritime transport or higher consequence activities in marine bottoms such as dredging. The lower sections of the different estuaries were also classified as medium to high-risk areas, particularly in the Lima, Cávado and Douro estuaries. The results also showed that several sections of the coast are already at high risk from human activities, particularly in the central and southern coastal regions.

In the Current management narrative, approximately 25% of the region is classified as high risk, while 50% is classified as medium and 25% as low risk areas. The different management narratives showed changes in the spatial distribution of the higher risk zones, with either an increase or reduction in the areas classified as high risk, depending on the narrative. Compared to the Current management narrative, the high-risk areas showed an increase of almost 18% in the BAU narrative. The MPA1 narrative showed a decrease of approximately 6% in classified high-risk areas in comparison to the Current narrative, while MPA2 narrative reduced high-risk areas by 18%. The MPA2rf narrative, which represents a compromise between conservation and the maintenance of low intensity fishing, showed a reduction of approximately 11% in classified higher risk areas.

Figure 3. Total cumulative risk (top) and reclassified risk (bottom) for the different management narratives modelled in this study, for the current climate conditions.

3.2 Future climatic scenarios ecosystem risk

Future climatic scenarios showed a general increase in the cumulative risk across the entire study area due to the addition of the climate-related pressures. This increase was discernible across the entire area but was particularly pronounced along the coastal interface (along some coastal segments and estuarine regions), due to the combined effect of both increased SST and the projected future coastal vulnerability increase (Figure 4).

In these future scenarios, the spatial variation in risk distribution in response to changes in the management narratives was more pronounced than that observed across the different future climatic scenarios (Figure 4). The inclusion of these climate-derived pressures increased the overall risk category in the area, in the already observed patterns of medium to higher risk areas. The combination of human activities and uses with the climate-induced pressures resulted in an increase in risk class for a given cell within the case study, leading to an increased occurrence of high-risk areas.

The intermediate severe climate scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP2-4.5), both in the near term (by year 2050) and long term (by year 2100), showed similar patterns of risk distribution across the entire case study area. However, the worst-case climatic scenario for the year 2100 (SSP5-8.5) showed most of the area (95%) classified as high risk in the Current management narrative and in both, the BAU and MPPA2rf narratives. The MPA1 and MPA2 narratives (prohibition of large-scale fisheries), maintained medium levels of risk across the modelled changes in human activities.

Figure 4. Total cumulative risk for the different management narratives and climate scenarios modelled in this study.

3.3 Habitat risk

The observed overall patterns of risk varied across habitats within the management narratives and climatic scenarios (Figure 5). Higher median risk scores are observed across beaches, aphotic soft and rock bottoms, and estuarine habitats, both pelagic and bottom. The higher median scores across these habitats and across management narratives indicate higher habitat areas at risk from the cumulative human activities and incorporated in this work. The spatial distribution of habitats higher risk areas followed the patterns observed for the ecosystem maps (as the overall risk to the ecosystem derived from the risk to the habitats). While higher risk areas for aphotic rock bottoms were located at the north of the study area, the aphotic soft bottoms higher risk areas were located at the southern end of the study area, although we could observe some heterogeneity across its distribution; the same was observed for the photic benthic habitats. Estuarine pelagic and bottom habitats had their higher risk scores near the estuarine mouth, while higher risk zones across beaches were scattered around the whole distribution of the habitat. On the other hand, both soft and rock photic bottoms habitats and saltmarshes had the lowest median cumulative risk values across the different scenarios. Similar to their aphotic counterparts, the higher risk areas across photic soft bottoms are mainly distributed at the southern portion of the study case area, while photic rock bottoms higher risk areas are located at the northern portion of the habitat limits. Saltmarsh high-risk areas are mainly found at their edges, although for the river Cávado saltmarsh higher risk were obtained across the whole saltmarsh.

As with the total risk to the entire ecosystem, there was a higher heterogeneity of cumulative risk changes across management narratives, than between climatic scenarios. There was also a general increase in the risk scores of habitats across nearly all habitats with the increasing severity of the climatic scenarios. The increase in risk across habitats in the BAU management narrative was evident across all habitats in the study. We observed that changes in human activities and uses across the management narratives reduced the risk scores across habitats when compared to the Current management situation. However, these changes in risk to habitats were more pronounced for aphotic bottom habitats, photic soft bottoms and marine pelagic habitats. In these habitats, the reduced pressures from activities within the MPA1 and MPA2 management narratives were more clearly highlighted. In contrast, the MPA2rf management narrative values for the different habitats

were similar and, in some cases, slightly below the individual habitat risk scores in comparison with the Current management narrative.

Across the case study habitats, the increase in SST, coastal exposure to SLR and extreme events, maritime transport and fishing are the stressors that contribute to the highest risk (Figure 6). For bottom aphotic and photic habitats SST, fishing and maritime transport were the greatest contributors to the habitat risk. In contrast, for intertidal habitats (beaches, intertidal rocks and sand and saltmarshes), SST, coastal exposure, recreation and the presence and pollution derived from artificial areas were the main contributors to the cumulative risk in these habitats. For coastal dunes the higher contributors to the risk in these habitats were coastal exposure, SST and the artificial and agricultural areas. For the pelagic habitats, both marine and estuarine, the highest contributors to risk were the increases in SST, fishing, maritime transport and coastal exposure.

Deconstructing the risk into its exposure and consequence scores shows that for all the stressors that account for the risk to habitats across the management narratives under the Present climatic conditions, the mean exposure score ranged from 0 to 2.4 (Figure S8). On the other hand, the mean consequence scores were consistently lower, ranging from 0 to 2.01. When considering the inclusion of the Climatic scenarios across all the management scenario narratives, these values increased. The mean maximum exposure range increased to 3 and the consequence mean score maximum value increased to 2.63.

Figure 5. The distribution of cumulative risk for each realm and for the total ecosystem in each management narrative and climatic scenario. The shaded areas correspond to the 25th to 75th percentiles, excluding the outliers. The category “Coastal” includes intertidal sands and rocks, coastal dunes and beaches. The category “Estuaries” include estuarine pelagic and bottoms, and saltmarshes. The category “Marine” include pelagic marine, Aphotic Rock Bottoms, Aphotic Soft Bottoms, Photic Rock Bottoms, and Photic Soft Bottoms.

Figure 6: Contribution of the different pressures to the total risk for each habitat type considered in this study.

4 Discussion

This study represents a novel assessment of the cumulative risk to habitats and the ecosystem in coastal and marine systems, by integrating both anthropogenic and climate-derived pressures, within different climatic scenarios and management narratives. Such approach allows a more holistic understanding of the spectrum of risk across scenarios and management actions, and it provides a valuable support for adaptive management in the northern coastal and marine region of Portugal and elsewhere, and the support for both EBM approaches and MSP and ICM practices.

The ecosystem risk is most pronounced along some areas in the marine region, particularly in the southern marine region of the study case area, which had multiple marine activities and uses, particularly from overlapping of different fishery types (e.g. gillnets, purse-seiners). Additionally, higher risk areas were also found along the coastal segments where multiple stressors co-occur in close proximity. The risk distribution aligns with the results of other studies focused on Portuguese maritime space and coasts, although performed at a coarse resolution (Batista et al., 2014; Fernandes et al., 2017; Genua-Olmedo et al., 2023; Willaert et al., 2019). Habitats most at risk include beaches, aphotic soft and rock bottoms, and estuarine pelagic and bottom habitats, with the level of risk varying spatially within the habitats footprints. These findings are consistent with other studies assessing the cumulative impact on marine and coastal habitats in this coastal region and elsewhere, highlighting the increased vulnerability of coastal habitats to increased pressures (Arkema et al., 2014; Batista et al., 2014; Fernandes et al., 2017; Halpern et al., 2015; Wyatt et al., 2017).

This increased risk could cause potentially adverse changes to the provision of ecological functions by the habitats and the species inhabiting them, ultimately reducing their capacity to provide ES and in turn, SGB (Cormier et al., 2013; Elliott and O'Higgins, 2020; Griffiths et al., 2017; Molony et al., 2022). This is especially the case since some of the identified high-risk areas are classified as hotspots for ES and SGB provision, such as coastal protection in some of the coastal stretches (Cunha et al., 2023, 2021), or biodiversity, such as the southern portion of the marine area or the estuarine regions (Amorim et al., 2018; Gomes et al., 2018; Ramos et al., 2010). This is of particular concern, especially given the potential synergistic effects of stressors that can occur at some locations. For example, at the coastal habitats such as dunes and beaches, the synergistic effects of increased pressure from human settlements and recreational activities, coupled with the

erosion of coasts due to high energy waves and sediment deficit (Marinho et al., 2019), could put at risk important coastal habitats that currently protect against further erosion (Cunha et al., 2021).

In the marine areas studied, habitat risk results from a few high-consequence activities, which allows for a targeted management of their potential spatial co-allocation and of their spatial extents and pressures. In contrast, nearshore and coastal habitats were classified as being at higher risk due to the multiple stressors and cumulative pressures, that simultaneously and cumulatively could compromise their GES under the MSFD implementation (Côté et al., 2016; Halpern et al., 2019; Korpinen et al., 2021; Stelzenmüller et al., 2020). This multitude of pressures presents an increased challenge for stakeholders and decision-makers in establishing management priorities, which may involve reducing or adjusting activity intensity and frequency or managing their spatial overlaps. These decisions, while potentially leading to conflicts (although compatible uses may also exist), must be addressed to maintain the ecosystem GES, particularly at coastal-sea interfaces. In these, due to the multiple legislative instruments, such as coastal integrative management, urban planning, protected areas management, WFD or the MSFD, and the multiple sectoral activities must be integrated to harmonize the management of these regions (Elliott et al., 2023, 2020; Hodgson et al., 2019; Villasante et al., 2022). By integrating the multitude of human activities and uses in marine and coastal regions and assessing their cumulative effects on habitats and species that provide ES and SGB, managers can prioritize the most significant threats and devise effective management strategies to increasing pressures to safeguard long-term system productivity (Frazão Santos et al., 2020; Levin et al., 2020; Pinarbaşı et al., 2017; Queirós et al., 2022, 2021).

Across the management and climatic scenarios, our study consistently identified increases in SST, increasing coastal exposure to SLR and storms and extreme events, large-scale fishing and maritime transport as significant contributors to risk across habitats. These causes of pressure are similar to related studies assessing cumulative impacts on marine and coastal systems (Fernandes et al., 2017; Genua-Olmedo et al., 2023; Halpern et al., 2019; Korpinen et al., 2021). For example, Batista et al., (2014) and Fernandes et al., (2017) in two risk assessments of the Portuguese coast, also found fisheries among the highest impact scores on habitats, and a higher risk in coastal zones. On the other hand, we also observed that changes in management approaches had a more pronounced effect on the spatial patterns of risk than the inclusion of climate change-derived pressures, with the last having an additive effect on the habitat risk and overall ecosystem risk

(Gissi et al., 2021; Mach et al., 2017; Piggott et al., 2015; Wakelin et al., 2015). Incorporating the climate-derived external pressures altered the spatial distribution of high-risk zones at the land-sea interface, while in marine areas, it amplified the overall risk scores without altering the observed risk patterns from human activities. This raises the attention of decision-makers and managers to the importance of balancing our uses of coastal and marine systems with the maintenance of the natural capital, to allow these systems to be able to cope with the added pressures of climate change. For example, the coastal-sea interface in our case study area is already acknowledged to be under substantial erosion pressure and susceptible to overtopping and extreme events, and future climate-derived pressures is expected to intensify these challenges (Cunha et al., 2021; Marinho et al., 2019; Tavares et al., 2021). This underlines the urgent need for quantitative tools such as the one used in this study, which can assist policymakers and stakeholders in devising adaptive management strategies to address current system pressures effectively while preparing for future challenges (Borja et al., 2024; Galparsoro et al., 2025; Lubchenco and Grorud-Colvert, 2015).

In this case study, the addition of climate-related pressures was additive, reflecting the widespread distribution of the external pressures considered (Elliott, 2011; Halpern et al., 2015; Micheli et al., 2013), but also a result of the employed methodology (Arkema et al., 2014; Natural Capital Project, 2023). Although climate-derived pressures often exacerbate system pressures and also on their ecosystem components, the opposite has also been observed in some studies (Corrales et al., 2017). Significant knowledge gaps still persist regarding the cumulative effects on habitats and species and the interplay between human-induced and climate change pressures (Gissi et al., 2021; Rilov et al., 2020; Wilson et al., 2020), which limits the integration of climate change exogenic pressures into MSP and EBM practices. The highly mixed and non-linear effects of these cumulative pressures, with unknown responses from habitats, species or the entire ecosystem (Côté et al., 2016; Hewitt et al., 2016; Teichert et al., 2016), introduce uncertainties in these cumulative assessments, highlighting the need for further studies on the topic, particularly the responses of the system regarding the effects on the delivery of ES and SGB (Borja et al., 2024; Frazão Santos et al., 2022; Gissi et al., 2021). Despite these challenges, the application and operationalization of cumulative risk-based assessments are crucial for supporting ecosystem management, particularly in the context of MSP, MSFD, EBM and ICM within marine and coastal systems (Galparsoro et

al., 2025, 2021; Stelzenmüller et al., 2020). These approaches offer support and facilitate the planning, regulation, and risk analysis of human uses and activities, aiding in the analysis of trade-offs for the considered management options, given the importance that these had in the quantification of the risk to the ecosystem within this study.

The growing emphasis on advancing Blue Growth initiatives and expanding the utilization of marine space and natural capital, and human activities calls for a balanced management of risks while maintaining human activities (European Commission, 2012; Galparsoro et al., 2021; Queirós et al., 2022; Rickels et al., 2019). It is essential that the current management of marine and coastal activities is guided by practices that ensure the prevention of escalating system pressures, due to their contribution to the system overall risk. Additional future pressures posed by climate change could be mitigated to avoid reaching tipping points and the occurrence of regime shifts, which could disrupt the system's capacity to support these activities (Miller et al., 2016; Nes et al., 2016; Stelzenmüller et al., 2020; Thrush et al., 2021). Risk assessments offering potential future scenarios to managers should be used in effective and preemptive management of coastal and marine systems (Cormier et al., 2013). These can better prepare the regional natural and social capital for future changes, even with the current uncertainties associated. This could include assessing both high and low-risk future ecosystem risks and exploring strategies to reduce the impact of activities, anticipating climate-driven shifts in human activities, such as fishing (Tittensor et al., 2021; Wakelin et al., 2015), or even the redefinition of MPA, aiming to establish climate refugia areas (Frazão Santos et al., 2020; Rilov et al., 2020; Tulloch et al., 2020).

The application of a cumulative risk-based assessment followed here, however, also has model assumptions and some limitations (Hodgson and Halpern, 2019). The model solely evaluates the risk of stressor overlap in space, potentially oversimplifying the assessment by neglecting indirect effects, and failing to predict potential habitat responses or adaptations to stressors, ignoring the historical legacy of human activities on habitats that could influence habitat responses and recovery parameters (Kelly, 2019; Natural Capital Project, 2023; Turschwell et al., 2021). It also does not fully include the temporal aspects of the activity and the pressure footprints and may require a more complete weighting to account for synergistic and antagonistic interactions between activities and their pressures (Elliott et al., 2020). As such, the model assumes an additive interaction between stressors due to the limited understanding of synergistic or antagonistic effects.

Model accuracy and results are dependent on data quality, which was addressed using a data quality score, included in the model. However, for instance, marine bottom habitat distribution data are limited to general categories, lacking detailed information on particularly important habitats such as rock reefs and kelps (Franco et al., 2018; Pinho et al., 2016). Similarly, the SST projections derived from a single model (CNRM/CM2/1/HR, Voldoire et al., 2019), may not fully capture small potential changes across the region, particularly in intermediate scenarios. This resulted in small SST differences from the 2010-2014 reference period and weak changes in the final risk scores, except under the most severe scenario (SST5-8.5).

Moreover, future pressures from climate change, such as ocean acidification (Gao et al., 2019; Kapsenberg and Cyronak, 2019; Koenigstein et al., 2016), changes in salinity (Anastácio et al., 2013; Vargas et al., 2017), and the formation of anoxic zones (Cheung et al., 2022; Vedor et al., 2021; Zakem et al., 2020), were not incorporated, due to lack of spatial explicit data, but should be considered in future studies due to their potential impacts on marine organisms and their distribution. It is possible that some of these, such as ocean acidification, may be regarded as being uniform over a hydrodynamically well-mixed area. Finally, the scores used to construct habitat and stressor exposure and consequence tables, while based on expert judgment and available literature, are subject to uncertainties regarding site-specific habitat responses to stressors, which may introduce uncertainties into the final cumulative risk scores (Jones et al., 2018; Kallio et al., 2025; Natural Capital Project, 2023). Consequently, the effectiveness and readiness of management areas to respond to increasing pressures on marine and coastal systems will be enhanced by including additional high-quality data sources. The development and application of emerging technologies could help researchers evaluate more complex scenarios and devise new approaches for cumulative risk assessments (Peterson et al., 2020; Zennaro et al., 2021). With the current worldwide development in digitalization and additional data sources from in situ and remote sensors, large volumes of data could be available to build systems that could help research and policymaking tackle these complex cumulative pressures problems. Although this study did not quantify the potential reduction in ES and SGB of increasing risks, such valuation and the potential trade-offs associated with the management options should be considered (see also Cunha et al., (2023)). In particular, management is more difficult to harmonize, at the coastal interface where multiple activities overlap although an aim should be to achieve either coherent or

equivalent management actions (Elliott et al., 2023). Despite its limitations, the InVEST HRA model offers a practical and transferable tool for cumulative risk-based assessments that can inform and support policies and management. For example, it has already supported policies in Belize (Arkema et al., 2014); and in the New Hampshire Great Bay to identify areas of high risk to prioritize management and restoration efforts (NOAA, 2016). It provides a valuable tool to assess the major pressures on marine and coastal resources, from current and future pressures, as also observed in this study. It also facilitates the creation of scenarios around management decisions and their potential risks to ecosystems and the analysis of trade-offs, aiding in the integrative management of all activities and land-sea interactions at the land-sea continuum. It can also enable stakeholders to focus and prioritize management efforts to mitigate risk at higher risk areas, e.g. the coastal region and the southern marine area in this case study, enabling the development of mitigation strategies for addressing the increase of risk due to future changes that could prevent achieving GES of marine and coastal waters.

5 Conclusions

Our findings indicate the presence of considerable ecosystem risks in certain marine areas and coastal segments, particularly impacting beaches, aphotic soft and rock bottoms, and estuaries. The results of this study indicate that existing local stressors may have a more pronounced impact on risks to the ecosystem, and that climate change pressures may intensify the risk profile of areas already deemed to be high-risk, particularly at the coastal-sea interface. The key risk factors across management and climate scenarios included the locally unmanaged pressures of rising sea surface temperatures and increased coastal exposure to sea-level rise and storms, and the manageable stressors such as fishing, tourism, urbanization and maritime transport. Conservation scenarios (MPA1, MPA2 and MPA2rf) show a consequent decrease in areas classified as high risk. While the most restrictive management scenarios could reduce the occurrence of high-risk areas between 6% and 18%, the MPA2rf scenario, a compromise between conserving the regional natural capital and maintaining current socio-economic activities at lower intensity levels, could reduce the occurrence of high-risk areas by 11%. This should prompt managers to require careful analysis and management of ecosystem risks in order to maintain the resistance and resilience of the system and its ability to provide ES against future increasing pressures, as highlighted by this study.

Promoting Blue Growth and the increasing number of human uses and activities in coastal and marine regions need to be carefully assessed and managed as such to prevent future climate change impacts from pushing ecosystems beyond tipping points and disrupting important ecological functions, thereby affecting the provision of ES and SGB. Despite gaps in the knowledge of how habitats and species will respond to the combined effects of human activities and climate-related pressures, policymakers and managers must adopt a precautionary approach to anticipate future changes. By integrating such assessments within the development of management narratives and future climate scenarios, as in this study, policymakers and managers can enhance their ability to manage, predict and address the changes in the distribution of areas at risk, thereby ensuring the long-term sustainable use of marine and coastal ecosystems.

Acknowledgments

This research was partially supported by national funds through FCT – Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology within the scope of UIDB/04423/2020, UIDP/04423/2020, IDB/04033/2020, UIDP/04033/2020, LA/P/0101/2020 and by JC Ph.D. fellowship from FCT Do*Mar (ref. PD/BD/150359/2019, co-financed by FSE through Programa Operacional Regional Norte). This work is also supported by National Funds by FCT – Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology, under the projects UID/04033: Centro de Investigação e de Tecnologias Agro-Ambientais e Biológicas and LA/P/0126/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/LA/P/0126/2020>). This study has also received support from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° GA 101082048. The contribution of ME was funded in part under the EU HorizonEurope GES4SEAS and MarinePlan projects (<https://www.ges4seas.eu/>; <https://www.marineplan.eu/>) through the UKRI Grant Agreements N° 10050522 and 10050537 respectively. SV thanks the financial support of the EU Atlanteco project through the Grant Agreement N° 862923. The authors also acknowledge the time and constructive feedback from three anonymous reviewers that greatly helped to improve the quality of this manuscript.

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